

Effect of temperature on the sorption behavior of sulfate in some soils of West Bengal

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Adsorption maximum of sulfate is higher in inceptisols followed by alfisols and entisols being higher at low temperature (293 K). Bonding energy constants are of very low values in all the soils. The results also show highest negative ΔG° values in alfisols at 318 K and the lowest in entisols at 293 K. ΔH° and ΔS° changes are higher in alfisols followed by entisols and inceptisols.

Adsorption and desorption mechanisms of sulfate in soils control the availability of sulfur and the soil properties largely influence the processes^{1,2}. The availability of sulfur in soils depends upon the inherent availability of sulfur and sorption behavior of soils. Various soil properties affect the sorption of sulfate^{3,4}. But very little information is available regarding the effect of temperature affecting the adsorption and desorption of sulfate in soils. Keeping this in view, the present investigation was undertaken to study the effect of temperature on the sorption behaviour of added sulfate in soils of different agrochemical zones of West Bengal.

Results and Discussion

The physicochemical properties of the soils are presented in Table 1. The results (Table 2) showed that the amount of $\text{SO}_4\text{-S}$ concentration in equilibrium solution was recorded higher with the corresponding decrease in the adsorbed $\text{SO}_4\text{-S}$ content in the soil, having higher decrease with increasing temperature irrespective of the nature of soils. Among the three soils, inceptisols showed a relatively higher amount of adsorbed $\text{SO}_4\text{-S}$ with simultaneous decrease in the concentration of $\text{SO}_4\text{-S}$ in the equilibrium solution than that of alfisols and entisols. With temperature variation, the adsorption behavior of $\text{SO}_4\text{-S}$ varied greatly in all soils (being lower at high temperature (318 K)). However, the results of $\text{SO}_4\text{-S}$ adsorption exhibited a linear form of Langmuir equation which also supports the results reported^{5,6}. The lower amount of $\text{SO}_4\text{-S}$ adsorbed in alfisol of Jhargram might be due to lesser affinity of $\text{SO}_4\text{-S}$ with the soil solid phase caused by the formation of complex ion by sulfate with organic matter that are occurring, particularly 2–25 mg dm^{-3} applied $\text{SO}_4\text{-S}$ concentration range.

After exceeding the capacity of such complex ion formation with the addition of sulfur (50 mg dm^{-3}), the soil colloidal particles take part in the competition and begin to adsorb more $\text{SO}_4\text{-S}$ till it appears to be saturated at 100 mg dm^{-3} . Similar observations were also reported by previous workers^{1,2}.

Table 1. Physicochemical properties of soils

Soil	pH	Silt %	Clay %	Org. C g kg ⁻¹	Free MnO ₂ g kg ⁻¹	Free Al ₂ O ₃ g kg ⁻¹	Amorph Fe g kg ⁻¹	Cryst. Fe g kg ⁻¹	CEC
Inceptisols	7.5	18.6	24.6	6.56	0.32	10.20	2.92	10.91	14.8
Alfisols	6.6	17.8	28.2	5.98	0.21	16.80	4.33	14.20	16.7
Entisols	5.7	14.6	16.4	4.81	0.26	12.21	3.64	9.72	10.6

Table 2. Effect of temperature on equilibrium parameters for sulfate adsorption

Soil	Amt. of sulfate added mg dm ⁻³	C mg dm ⁻³			C/q g dm ⁻³		
		293	308	318 K	293	308	318 K
Inceptisols	100	65.5	67.0	71.0	0.19	0.20	0.25
	50	35.5	36.0	40.0	0.23	0.26	0.40
	25	19.0	20.0	21.5	0.32	0.40	0.61
	10	6.3	6.8	7.8	0.17	0.21	0.34
	5	3.0	3.3	3.7	0.12	0.17	0.28
	2	0.9	1.1	1.4	0.08	0.12	0.23
Alfisols	100	70.0	71.5	74.4	0.23	0.25	0.29
	50	38.0	39.0	41.2	0.32	0.35	0.41
	25	21.5	22.0	21.8	0.61	0.73	0.68
	10	8.0	8.5	8.6	0.40	0.57	0.62
	5	3.5	4.0	4.3	0.23	0.40	0.61
	2	1.2	1.5	1.6	0.17	0.30	0.47
Entisols	100	71.5	72.5	73.4	0.25	0.26	0.28
	50	39.0	40.0	40.7	0.35	0.40	0.44
	25	20.5	21.0	22.2	0.46	0.52	0.79
	10	8.0	8.5	8.7	0.40	0.57	0.67
	5	3.5	3.9	4.1	0.23	0.35	0.46
	2	1.2	1.4	1.6	0.17	0.26	0.40

The results (Table 3) showed that the amount of sulfate adsorption was higher at lower temperature (293 K) in all the soils excepting in alfisols of Jhargram where it showed an increased adsorption with increasing temperature. Adsorption maxima varied from 77.51 to 53.19, 46.92 to 50.68 and 31.15 to 25.69 mg g⁻¹ at 293 and 318 K in inceptisols, alfisols and entisols, respectively. However, the adsorption maxima (Q) did not show so much of variation due to increase in temperature upto 308 K in inceptisols and entisols, while the same varied drastically in alfisols where much lower values of adsorption maxima were recorded at 308 and 318 K. Although, the adsorption maxima values were much lower in alfisols but the amount of SO₄-S adsorption was higher than that of entisols which might be due to very little adsorption sites available as well as low amount of clay organic carbon content and cation exchange capacity (CEC) value⁶ in the latter soil. Again, the higher adsorption maxima (Q) in inceptisols and entisols particularly at low temperature (293 K) may be attributed to the rapid physical adsorption which decreased with increasing temperature.

Table 3. Langmuir and thermodynamic parameters for sulfate adsorption

Soil	Temp K	Q mg g ⁻¹	$b \times 10^2$ dm ³ mg ⁻¹	$-\Delta G$ kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Inceptisols	293	77.51	16.47	1.05		
	308	69.33	12.82	1.26	4.15	17.73
	318	53.19	9.25	1.51		
Alfisols	293	46.92	12.53	1.21		
	308	50.63	6.15	1.72	8.12	31.86
	318	50.68	4.19	2.02		
Entisols	293	31.15	25.71	0.79		
	308	22.49	23.65	0.88	5.09	19.91
	318	25.69	12.06	1.34		

The bonding energy constant (b) for sulfate adsorption varied considerably in all the soils due to variation in temperature, being varied from 0.16 to 0.09, 0.12 to 0.041 and 0.25 to 0.12 dm³ mg⁻¹ in inceptisols, alfisols and entisols at 293 and 318 K, respectively, indicating that sulfate adsorption takes place less rigidly by various soil components, viz. clay colloids, organic matter etc. in alfisols than that in inceptisols and entisols and hence exhibited such low value of bonding constant in alfisols.

The standard free energy (ΔG°) changes were negative in all the three soils suggesting that the adsorption of SO₄-S was spontaneous. The magnitude of such negativity of ΔG° changes varied with temperature from -1.05 to -1.51, -1.21 to -2.02 and -0.79 to -1.34 kcal mol⁻¹ in inceptisols, alfisols and entisols at 293 to 318 K, respectively. Decrease in ΔG° provides a measure of decrease in the concentration of adsorbate in the solution phase⁸. Alfisols showed higher negative value of free energy (2.02 kcal mol⁻¹) at higher

temperature (318 K) while entisols showed the lowest (-1.34 kcal mol⁻¹). Such higher negative value in alfisols at all temperatures suggested that the adsorption of SO₄-S exhibited more spontaneous nature resulting in greater retention of SO₄-S by adsorbent than that of inceptisols and entisols. The enthalpy change (ΔH°) for sulfate adsorption of a standard adsorption process showed positive values in all the soils suggesting adsorption of SO₄-S to be an endothermic process and the values 4.15, 8.12 and 5.09 kcal mol⁻¹ in inceptisols, alfisols and entisols, respectively, suggest the heat of adsorption to follow the order: alfisols > inceptisols > entisols. The values of entropy change (ΔS°) was positive for all soils, being 17.73, 31.86 and 19.91 cal K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ in inceptisols, alfisols and entisols, respectively, suggesting a higher degree of disorderliness in the adsorption of SO₄-S in alfisols followed by entisols and inceptisols.

The results suggested that the amount of SO₄-S adsorbed was lower in alfisols owing to low bonding energy constant, higher negative values of ΔG in comparison to inceptisols and entisols.

Experimental

The soils were collected (0–15 cm depth) from three locations of West Bengal, viz. inceptisols (Kalyani), alfisols (Jhargram) and entisols (Toophanganj), for adsorption and desorption studies of sulfate at 293, 308 and 318 K.

Adsorption study: Each soil sample (5 g) was taken in a series of polyethylene centrifuge tube (100 ml capacity) and different concentrations of sulfate solutions (1, 0.5, 0.25, 0.1, 0.05 and 0.02 μg g⁻¹) in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ CaCl₂ (50 ml) to maintain the ionic strength in the solution were added to each tube. All the tubes containing three soils and respective sulfate treatments were replicated twice and kept at room temperature (293 ± 1 K) and higher temperature (318 ± 1 K) in the B.O.D. incubator overnight. The tubes were then shaken for 3 h and centrifuged after 1 h. The supernatant solution (5 ml) was pipetted out from each tube and the sulfate determined turbidimetrically¹⁰. Adsorption of sulfate in soils were studied following the Langmuir adsorption equation¹¹,

$$C/q = 1/Qb + C/Q$$

where C is the equilibrium concentration, q the amount of sulfate adsorbed per unit mass of soil, Q the adsorption maxima and b the constant related to bonding energy. Q and b values were calculated from the plot of C/q vs C . Thermodynamic parameters associated with the adsorption, e.g. free energy changes (ΔG°) were calculated¹² from the variation of equilibrium constant related to bonding energy (b) with change in temperature together with standard enthalpy change (ΔH°) and standard entropy change (ΔS°) as explained by Biggar and Cheung¹³.

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